

SKILLS OF ORGANIZING CULTURAL EVENTS

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Abstract. This article talks about the art of organizing cultural events and the forms of public holidays and celebrations.

Key words: cultural events, skill, disco club, artistic composition.

НАВЫКИ ОРГАНИЗАЦИИ КУЛЬТУРНЫХ МЕРОПРИЯТИЙ

Аннотация. В статье говорится об искусстве организации культурных мероприятий и формах проведения народных праздников и торжеств.

Ключевые слова: культурные мероприятия, мастерство, диско-клуб, художественная композиция.

Cultural events help people to provide them with necessary information, artistic-aesthetic pleasure, involve them in cultural-creative work and have meaningful leisure time. These events mainly consist of such forms as oral journals, club nights, artistic compositions, artistic agitbrigade and disco club programs, theatrical concerts and performances, folk traditions, public holidays and elections. Artistic and public events include the main and many forms of cultural and educational institutions.

The most advantageous aspect of cultural events is that they more embody the activities of cultural and educational institutions. In particular, activities such as agitation and propaganda work, amateur creativity, meaningful organization of free time are combined in them. If we refer to every form of artistic and public events (public holidays, traditional ceremonies, theatrical performances, various parties, demonstrations), they contain agitation-propaganda content, results of amateur creativity, facilities created for artistic-aesthetic enjoyment and recreation. can be clearly felt. Therefore, the artistic and public event is a generalized reflection of all activities in cultural and educational institutions.

Practical organization of cultural events is a creative organization of concrete forms of work based on theory and methodology. Getting into practice is the third process.

Thus, achieving the organization of artistic and public events includes the following processes:

- 1.Learning theoretical and scientific foundations (including work experience).
- 2.Mastering general and specific methodology (including advanced work experience).
- 3.To have a creative approach to work, practical organization skills.

These interrelated processes and related issues are the object of this study guide.

Therefore, this guide, which aims to reflect the theory, methodology and practical experience of art-public events, consists of three chapters.

In the first chapter, issues related to the theory of cultural activities were covered.

It describes the scientific-theoretical foundations, including the role of activities in social and cultural life, their general and specific principles, as well as concrete functions.

In the second chapter, the main stages of the methodology and process of preparing cultural events, i.e., the laws and regulations of creating a scenario and its post-production (directing), were studied in a scientific and methodical way. Also, the used methods and tools were explained.

In the third chapter, the main forms of cultural activities were given a separate and detailed description. The essence, brief history, specific characteristics and educational possibilities of each form were studied.

Cultural and educational institutions are one of the main links of the system of ideological and educational work, they play an important role in the socio-cultural life of the people, meaningful organization of free time of workers. They carry out the process of all-round development of a person and increase of socio-cultural activity through specific tasks, i.e. providing continuous education and training, engaging in amateur creativity and organizing meaningful rest and recreation.

Cultural and educational activities are, first of all, activities of cultural and educational institutions - clubs, parks, museums, libraries and cultural complexes.

Not only clubs, parks, library institutions and cultural complexes, but also other social institutions and organizations are engaged in cultural and educational activities.

All the above-mentioned state institutions, trade unions, Komsomol organizations, voluntary societies, mass media, art institutions, educational institutions, industrial enterprises and many other organizations are involved in cultural and educational activities. They are engaged in as part of their work. Therefore, cultural-educational work occupies an important place in the life of all collectives as cultural-educational work.

Since cultural and educational activity is a multifaceted socio-cultural process, it is related to almost all spheres of life. First of all, it is related to people's work and free time. Cultural and educational activities help people to meaningfully organize their free time, provide meaningful rest and achieve good results in production. Celebrates the victories achieved at work, promotes the best practices among the public.

Secondly, it is a component of national culture. Cultural and educational works preserve, develop and promote the best progressive folk traditions created by mankind. It not only creates conditions for the public to enjoy the examples of culture, but also helps it to become a builder of cultural life, creates facilities for the formation of cultural image - behavior, manners and morals.

Thirdly, it is related to art. Along with the promotion of folk art, cultural and educational activities attract the public to various artistic amateur activities and develop their creativity.

There are many amateur associations for residents: clubs and studios. They create opportunities to create real examples of the people's art.

Fourth, it is related to lifestyle and local life. Cultural and educational works realistically reflect the life of a particular institution, collective, family and individual. It helps them solve the problems they face. It enriches the local life with spiritual content and decorates it artistically.

Fifth, it is related to physical education and sports. In particular, rural cultural and educational institutions are directly engaged in physical culture and sports, and play a major role in physical training and health of the population.

Cultural and educational work is not only related to all aspects of social and cultural life, but it is also directly related to many sciences.

Cultural and educational works use the scientific foundations, achievements, and experiences of sociology, pedagogy, psychology, and art studies. To study the needs of various associations, groups and classes among the public from sociology; how to carry out general pedagogy education and training; how to influence a person's mood and mind from psychology; learns the secrets of artistic art, organization of the creative process, etc. from art history.

Thus, cultural-educational work is a multifaceted cultural-social phenomenon, which creates its own theory using the scientific foundations of social sciences.

Cultural and educational work has its own object, subject and work activity.

Cultural and educational activities mainly consist of the following activities:

1. Carrying out campaigning and promotion work.
2. Cultivation of folk art.
3. Organization of workers' rest.

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The second type of classification is formed based on the use of effective tools and methods in the forms of cultural and educational work? This type of classification belongs to agitation and propaganda work in cultural and educational institutions. In this regard, work forms are divided into three: monologic, dialogic, and complex forms.

1. Monological forms are activities that provide information to the audience through the oral, "live" words of the speaker and other effective means. For example: lecture, document, information, etc.

2. Dialogic forms - these activities mainly consist of communication, discussion, exchange of ideas, which include conversations, discussions, meetings, and question-and-answer evenings.

3. By complex forms, in addition to the use of monologic and dialogic speeches, many other effective tools can be used. For example: oral journal, thematic party, etc.

Common forms in current cultural and educational work are mass forms of the first classification and complex forms of the second. They unite and create "artistic and public events".

The concept of "artistic and public events" helps to better reveal the essence of both public and complex forms of work in cultural and educational institutions. It should be noted that artistic-public events are still called "cultural-public events", "public events", "public forms" in practice.

Artistic and public events help people in their free time, provide them with the necessary information, provide them with artistic and aesthetic pleasure, involve them in cultural and creative work, and provide them with meaningful leisure. These events mainly consist of such forms as oral journals, club nights, artistic compositions, artistic agitbrigade and disco club programs, theatrical concerts and performances, folk traditions, public holidays and elections. Artistic and public events include the main and many forms of cultural and educational institutions.

The most advantageous aspect of artistic and public events is that they more embody the activities of cultural and educational institutions. In particular, activities such as agitation and propaganda work, amateur creativity, meaningful organization of free time are combined in them.

If we refer to every form of artistic and public events (public holidays, traditional ceremonies, theatrical performances, various parties, demonstrations), we can clearly see the content of agitation-propaganda, the results of amateur creativity, the facilities created for artistic-aesthetic enjoyment and recreation. can be felt. Therefore, the artistic and public event is a generalized reflection of all activities in cultural and educational institutions.

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